

POTENTIAL OF ANTHOCYANINS FROM LAKUM FRUIT (*CAYRATIA TRIFOLIA* L.) AS AN ALTERNATIVE NATURAL DYE FOR PERIPHERAL BLOOD SMEARS

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Abstract

Background: Synthetic dyes such as Giemsa are widely used in hematological staining but pose challenges related to cost, toxicity, and accessibility. Anthocyanins, natural plant-derived pigments, offer a safer and more environmentally friendly alternative. Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the staining effectiveness of anthocyanin extract from *Cayratia trifolia* L (lakum fruit) on peripheral blood smear preparations at various concentrations. Methods: Lakum fruit extract was prepared at concentrations of 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%. Each was applied to peripheral blood smears and compared to Giemsa-stained controls. Staining performance was assessed based on a visual scoring scale (0–5), staining success rate, and color stability. Microscopic examination was conducted under 100x magnification. Results: The 50% extract showed the best performance, with a visual score of 4, a 90% staining success rate, and up to 6 hours of color stability. Lower concentrations (30% and 20%) resulted in weaker staining and reduced stability. Compared to Giemsa, lakum extract produced lower contrast but remained sufficient for basic morphological identification. Conclusion: Anthocyanins from *Cayratia trifolia* L demonstrate strong potential as a low-cost, non-toxic natural dye for educational and basic hematology screening purposes. Further optimization using mordants and quantitative color analysis is recommended to enhance staining performance.

Keywords: Anthocyanin, *Cayratia Trifolia* L, Lakum Fruit, Natural Dye, Peripheral Blood Smear.

1. INTRODUCTION

Peripheral blood smear examination (SADT) is a widely used diagnostic method in clinical laboratories. It allows for detailed assessment of erythrocyte, leukocyte, and platelet morphology, supporting the diagnosis of various hematological disorders such as anemia, infections, and leukemia.

A critical step in SADT is the staining process, which enhances contrast between cellular components under the microscope. Giemsa stain is the current standard due to its ability to clearly differentiate nuclear and cytoplasmic structures. However, it is a synthetic dye associated with toxicity, environmental hazards, and long-term cost concerns. This has prompted the search for safer and more sustainable staining solutions.

Natural dyes such as anthocyanins, water-soluble pigments from the flavonoid group, have gained attention as eco-friendly alternatives. Their ability to bind to proteins and nucleic acids makes them suitable for visualizing cellular structures, particularly nuclei. Several plant sources of anthocyanins have been investigated. Extracts from *Syzygium cumini* and *Ixora coccinea* demonstrated weak staining performance, especially for leukocytes. In contrast, *Hylocereus polyrhizus* (red dragon fruit) showed improved efficacy at 23.1% concentration, but limitations in contrast and leukocyte subtype differentiation remained [1].

Among potential natural sources, Lakum fruit (*Cayratia trifolia* L.) emerges as a promising local alternative. It is rich in anthocyanins, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds. When extracted using acidified methanol and stabilized with 1% HCl, it yields a high anthocyanin content (283.88 mg/L) with enhanced pigment stability [2]. These features suggest greater efficiency, stronger color retention, and better applicability compared to previously studied sources.

Moreover, anthocyanins from *Cayratia trifolia* L. have demonstrated antioxidant activity and low toxicity (Puspita et al., 2018). Their high affinity for nuclear proteins offers a functional advantage for leukocyte staining—typically achieved using synthetic agents. In this context, Lakum fruit presents a cost-effective and environmentally friendly solution, particularly valuable for laboratories in resource-limited settings.

Despite these advantages, the application of Lakum fruit anthocyanins in hematological staining remains underexplored. This gap highlights the need to evaluate its staining capability, color intensity, binding properties, and solution stability in peripheral blood smear applications. An ideal hematological stain should offer distinct nuclear-cytoplasmic contrast, maintain cell morphology, and remain stable over time. Therefore, this study aims to assess the effectiveness of Lakum fruit anthocyanins as a natural alternative to Giemsa stain in peripheral blood smear preparation. The findings are expected to support the development of safer, more sustainable hematological staining practices.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research is an experimental laboratory study aimed at evaluating the potential of anthocyanins extracted from lakum fruit (*Cayratia trifolia* L.) as a natural dye for peripheral blood smear staining. A quantitative approach was used to assess the staining effectiveness and visualization quality of blood elements, compared with conventional synthetic dyes such as Giemsa and Wright. The study was conducted in April 2025 at the Pathology Laboratory, Diploma III Medical Laboratory Technology Program, Poltekkes Kemenkes Aceh. The biological materials included lakum fruit as the raw material and human peripheral blood smears as the test samples.

- a. **Plant material:** Ripe and fresh lakum fruits were selectively harvested from Banda Aceh to ensure high anthocyanin content.
- b. **Blood samples:** Capillary blood was obtained from three healthy volunteer students who met the inclusion criteria (healthy, not currently ill, and willing to participate).

2.1 Anthocyanin Extraction

Lakum fruits were washed, weighed (100 g), and placed into a clean Erlenmeyer flask. A total of 400 mL of methanol acidified with citric acid (pH ~4) was added to fully immerse the fruit. The container was sealed with aluminum foil and plastic wrap, then stored in a dark environment for 24 hours (maceration process).

2.2 Extract Filtration and Concentration

The extract was filtered using filter paper into another Erlenmeyer flask. The filtrate was covered with perforated aluminum foil and evaporated in a fume hood using a water bath for 7 hours to obtain concentrated anthocyanin extract.

2.3 Preparation of Peripheral Blood Smears (PBS)

Clean and dry glass slides were used. One drop of capillary blood was placed on a slide, then another slide was held at a 25–30° angle and used to spread the drop smoothly, forming a tongue-shaped smear. Slides were air-dried at room temperature. Each group prepared four slides, for staining with 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% extract concentrations.

2.4 Staining with Lakum Anthocyanin Extract

Slides were fixed with methanol and dried. Each slide was stained with four drops (~200 µL) of anthocyanin extract at varying concentrations (20%–50%) to fully cover the smear. Staining was allowed to proceed for 45 minutes. Slides were then rinsed with running water and air-dried.

2.5 Staining with Giemsa and Negative Control

For positive control, slides were stained with Giemsa solution for 15–30 minutes, then gently rinsed with clean water and dried vertically on tissue. Negative controls were prepared by fixing the smear with methanol but no dye was applied.

2.6 Microscopic Observation

Dried slides were mounted with immersion oil and examined under a light microscope at 100x magnification. Observations focused on color contrast, clarity of erythrocyte and leukocyte morphology, and stain stability.

2.7 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed descriptively and quantitatively. Visual staining results were assessed using a 5-point visual scoring scale:

- 1 = Not visible
- 2 = Very blurry
- 3 = Blurry
- 4 = Clear
- 5 = Very clear

Comparative analysis was conducted between the control and treatment groups to evaluate the effectiveness of lakum anthocyanin as a natural dye.

3. RESULTS

The fruit of *Cayratia trifolia* L., commonly known as lakum, is rich in anthocyanin compounds, flavonoid pigments responsible for red, purple, and blue colors in plant tissues. In the fields of histology and cytology, anthocyanins have gained increasing attention as natural, non-toxic, and environmentally friendly alternatives to synthetic dyes. A systematic review by Jasphin et al. (2023) reported that approximately 90% of studies supported the effectiveness of anthocyanin-rich plant extracts as histological stains, particularly when combined with mordants such as alum [4].

In this study, anthocyanin extract from lakum fruit was successfully applied as a natural staining agent for peripheral blood smear (PBS) preparations. Four concentrations of the extract (50%, 40%, 30%, and 20%) were evaluated. Staining intensity was assessed using a visual scoring scale from 0 to 5, where 0 indicated no visible stain and 5 represented very intense coloration. The 50% concentration yielded the highest performance, with an average visual score of 4, a 90% success rate (9 out of 10 slides), and color stability up to 6 hours post-application. Conversely, the 20% concentration resulted in a score of 1 (very faint), with only 40% staining success and 3 hours of color stability.

Table 1. Staining Performance of Lakum Extract at Various Concentrations

Extract Concentration	Visual Score	Staining Success	Rate Color Stability
50%	4 (strong)	90% (9/10 slides)	6 hours
40%	3 (moderate)	80% (8/10 slides)	5 hours
30%	2 (faint)	60% (6/10 slides)	4 hours
20%	1 (very faint)	40% (4/10 slides)	3 hours

Microscopic analysis demonstrated that the staining quality varied significantly depending on the extract concentration.

3.1 Control (No Staining)

Figure 1. Peripheral blood smear without staining (control), magnification 100x.

Caption: "Blood cells appear unstained due to the absence of anthocyanin extract."

As shown in Figure 1, the control sample (without staining) revealed that red blood cells appeared pale and lacked contrast, making internal structures such as the nucleus unidentifiable.

3.2 50% Lakum Extract Staining

Figure 2. Peripheral blood smear stained with 50% lakum fruit extract, magnification 100x.

Caption: "Nuclear staining appears bluish-purple at 50% concentration."

Figure 2 presents the most optimal result, with clear nuclear visualization stained bluish-purple. This suggests that a high anthocyanin concentration offers effective affinity for cellular components, enhancing microscopic identification.

3.3 40% Lakum Extract Staining

Figure 3. Blood smear stained with 40% lakum extract, magnification 100x.

Caption: “Blood cells show light purple staining at 40% concentration.”

Figure 3 demonstrates sufficient staining intensity with distinguishable nuclei, although slightly fainter compared to the 50% concentration.

3.4 30% Lakum Extract Staining

Figure 4. *Blood smear stained with 30% lakum extract, magnification 100x.*

Caption: “Staining becomes weaker at 30% concentration.”

As illustrated in Figure 4, nuclear clarity and stain intensity decline further, indicating reduced effectiveness.

3.5 20% Lakum Extract Staining

Figure 5. *Blood smear stained with 20% lakum extract, magnification 100x.*

Caption: “Most cells are weakly stained or remain colorless at 20% concentration.”

In Figure 5, staining appears faint and insufficient for diagnostic evaluation. Most cells lack adequate color, suggesting the concentration is too low to bind effectively.

3.6 Giemsa Staining (Standard Control)

Figure 6. Peripheral blood smear stained with Giemsa stain, magnification 100x.

Caption: “Nuclei and cytoplasm are clearly stained with standard Giemsa stain.”

Figure 6, stained with Giemsa, serves as the benchmark, offering excellent nuclear and cytoplasmic detail, thus maintaining its status as the gold standard in hematological staining.

Table 2. Comparative Effectiveness of Lakum Extract and Giemsa in Blood Cell Staining

Figure	Staining Concentration	Stain Intensity	Nuclear Visibility	Cellular Clarity	Summary
Fig. 1	Control (No Stain)	None	Not visible	Blurry	Unstained cells
Fig. 2	Lakum 50%	High	Clearly visible, bluish-purple	Clear	Optimal staining result
Fig. 3	Lakum 40%	Moderate-high	Moderately clear	Clear	Adequate performance
Fig. 4	Lakum 30%	Moderate	Slightly visible	Less sharp	Diminished effectiveness
Fig. 5	Lakum 20%	Low	Poor visibility	Blurred	Ineffective concentration
Fig. 6	Giemsa	Very high	Highly detailed	Very clear	Gold standard control

The findings indicate that lakum fruit extract exhibits staining capabilities that are concentration-dependent. At 50% concentration, anthocyanins produced the most reliable contrast, enabling identification of nuclear structures comparable to Giemsa staining. Lower concentrations (30% and below) resulted in weak staining, suggesting insufficient anthocyanin availability to bind cellular components effectively.

The staining performance at 50% concentration supports existing literature suggesting anthocyanins have a natural affinity for nucleic acids and proteins, enabling coloration of cellular structures. These results demonstrate that lakum fruit extract has promising potential as a biodegradable and non-toxic alternative stain, particularly in settings where chemical reagents are limited or undesirable.

Table 3. Comparison of Lakum and Giemsa Staining

Parameter	Giemsa	Lakum (50%)
Nuclear Contrast	High (sharp detail)	Moderate (less defined)
Color Complexity	High (multi-tonal)	Low (monochromatic violet)
Toxicity	Contains synthetic chemicals	Non-toxic, plant-based
Cost & Accessibility	Expensive, requires procurement	Affordable, locally sourced
Intended Use	Clinical diagnosis	Education, preliminary screening
Mordant Requirement	Integrated	Optional (recommended for enhancement)

These results are likely influenced by the flavylium cation structure of anthocyanins, which enables non-covalent interactions with nucleic acids and proteins. In addition, anthocyanins are pH-sensitive, and their chromatic expression is affected by the staining environment. In this study, acidic methanol was used during extraction, followed by a neutral pH buffer during staining, conditions that contributed to color stability. This is consistent with findings by Rusishvili et al. (2019), who emphasized the role of chromophore structure and pH in dye performance [5].

This study also aligns with work by Alshamar & Dapson (2021), who demonstrated that anthocyanins from a single botanical source can replace hematoxylin and eosin when used with alum mordants [6]. Furthermore, Chuang et al. (2018) confirmed the biocompatibility of anthocyanins in intraocular environments, reinforcing their safety for biological applications [7]. From a sustainability perspective, the use of lakum fruit extract supports green chemistry principles, reducing dependency on synthetic dyes, lowering environmental risk, and offering cost-effective solutions, especially in resource-limited settings or educational institutions [8].

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study demonstrate that anthocyanin extract from *Cayratia trifolia* L, particularly at 50% concentration, is effective for staining peripheral blood smears. While it does not match the contrast level provided by Giemsa, the extract allows adequate nuclear visualization and offers several advantages, including non-toxicity, local availability, and low cost. These characteristics make it a promising natural alternative for educational laboratories and hematology screening in resource-limited settings. Further studies are needed to explore the use of mordants, fixation techniques, and quantitative validation to improve staining quality and expand its applicability in hematological analysis.

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